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МЕТОДЫ АНАЛИЗА ФАКТОРОВ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЬСКИЙ РЫНОК

ANALYSIS METHODS OF THE FACTORS INFLUENCING ON CONSUMER MARKET

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Аннотация. В статье автором разработаны предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию методологии оценки рынка потребительских товаров с учетом особенностей региона; научно обоснованы региональные аспекты определения методов и направлений исследования рынка потребительских товаров; определена система факторов влияющих на формирование регионального рынка потребительских товаров, обоснованы рекомендации по прогнозированию тенденций развития рынка; даны рекомендации по организационным и экономическим направлениям развития рынка потребительских товаров области.

Научно обоснованные предложения и рекомендации, приведенные в статье, могут быть использованы при разработке мер по стабильному развитию регионального рынка потребительских товаров, а также при разработке учебных пособий и методических разработок.

Abstract. The results obtained and their novelty: proposals and recommendations for improving the methodology for assessing the market of consumer goods, taking into account the characteristics of the region; scientifically grounded regional aspects of determining methods and directions of research of the consumer goods market; a system of factors influencing the formation of the regional market of consumer goods is determined, recommendations for forecasting market development tendencies are grounded; recommendations on organizational and economic directions of development of the consumer goods market of the region are given.

The scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations given in the article can be used in developing measures for the stable development of the regional market of consumer goods, as well as in the development of teaching aids and methodological developments.

Ключевые слова: регион, потребительский рынок, территориальные особенности, рыночная конъюнктура, розничная торговля, оптовая торговля, конкурентоспособность.

Keywords: region, consumer market, territorial features, market conditions, retail trade, wholesale trade, competitiveness.

The location of production capacities across administrative divisions of the country plays an important socio-economic role in supplying the population with consumer goods. The further deepening of the reforms in the republic and the expansion of the liberalization of the economy influence the formation of the regional consumer goods market at different levels and levels. Satisfaction of the demand for the products of the community's life is the basis for any country and the basis of the welfare of the population. Therefore, the problem of market formation and development requires a serious approach.

The formation and enforcement of the regional consumer commodity market necessitates the need to explore the relationships between the processes and factors involved in the production, distribution, exchange and consumption of products in that region.

The regional consumer goods market is a complex system of interconnected exchange institutions. However, each participant has his own interests. Manufacturers try to get the money back and make a profit, while consumers are trying to meet their needs optimally.

Demonopolization, price liberalization, privatization of commercial enterprises and thus competition in the recent years have become a factor in the stabilization of the consumer market in the country, its mass consumption goods, the disruption of deficits, unsatisfied demand, and turnaround events. All of this defines the relevance of this dissertation.

Literature review

The issues of the formation and development of the regional consumer goods market are numerous in foreign and domestic markets has been and is being studied in the scientific researches of economical scientists of the republic. theory and methods of regional markets foreign scholars researched by S. Geytsman, R. F. Zakharov, O. A. Lomovtseva, T. G. Morozova, A. Nadein, M. Nikolaeva, A. Novoselov, V. Oreshin, T. Toda, M. Yu. Trubits, I. Sh. Shabunina, R. I. Shniper, G. G. Fetisov, A. Chaplin and others. The system of regional economies and markets in Uzbekistan were studied by several scientists as follow as M. A. Abdusalyamov, H. P. Abulkosimov, A. M. Alimov, I. V. Muyonenko, A. V. Vakhobov, T. M. Akhmedov, H. Nazarova, B. I. Norboev, D. N. Rahimov, A. M. Sodikov, A. Soliev, N. Tukhliev, A. Qayumov, A. Kodirov, Q. Hagberdiev, N. Kholmatov, F. Egamberdiev, Sh. Ermamatov. In the context of deepening economic reforms, scientific research works on the formation and development of such market relations as the financial market, the consumer goods market, economic security, economic integration and others are rising. However, issues related to the way the formation and development of the regional consumer goods market have been integrated into a single system and have not been sufficiently studied as a special research object. The relevance of this problem to the transition to a market economy and insufficient knowledge of economic literature led to the selection of research subjects.

Research Methods

In this research paper are used methods as: scientific abstracting, SWOT-analysis, scientific generalization and logical sequence.

Main part

The intensification of economic reforms should include a comprehensive study of the sources of income generation, consumption levels, trends in consumer demand, dynamics of the consumer market and its replenishment with competitive importers, enhancing the welfare of the population, socio-economic aspects of the administrative-territorial unit. the development of the country. The territorial consumer goods market is a part of the local socio-economic process and relations in the area of exchange, formed on the basis of demand and supply characteristics of the administrative-territorial structure. The need for commodities and services is directly related to the development and solvency of material and non-material production in the area. The solvent demand of the population is characterized by the amount of financial resources that it has acquired in goods and services. The requirements of socio-economic groups in the regions of the country are determined by the level of development of production capacities in these regions. One of the key features of the development of the regional market for products and services is the consistent expansion of the market capacity and the improvement of quality indicators. Each administrative-territorial unit is closely interconnected with the consumer goods market, which requires a preliminary study of the stages of the formation and development of the market at the national level. The new stage in the development of the consumer goods market in the republic can be divided into the following stages, recognizing the macroeconomic situation, the formation of market relations, the description of

structural changes, measures of saturation of the domestic market with domestic consumer goods, the global financial and economic crisis.

The first stage (1991-1994) was to preserve the potential for the production of consumer goods, abandon the former Soviet Union's ruble, which served as a means of dealing with sellers and buyers, to introduce national currency, to implement grain independence program, replace imported consumer goods development of manufacturing enterprises.

The second stage (1995-2000) is the priority development of the sectors producing consumer goods that form the basis of economic independence, the large-scale implementation of import-substitutive production strategies, increasing the inflow of investment into the production of non-foodstuffs, in particular, are characterized by practical work to meet local production.

The third stage (2001-2007) focuses on the establishment and development of export-oriented industries based on the development of import-substituting consumer goods. This stage is characterized by the privatization of large enterprises, limiting the monopoly position of state-owned companies, increasing the role of the private sector in the production of consumer goods, accelerating the process of liquidation of inefficient enterprises, reforming the organizational structure of the enterprise management, and the acceleration of the processes of localization of production.

The fourth stage (starting from 2008) is characterized by the development and implementation of programs to mitigate the global financial and economic crisis in the conditions of Uzbekistan, measures to overcome it, to modernize the country and bring it to the level of developed nations.

According to the author, the regional consumer goods market is a unified mechanism that provides a continuous process that satisfies the needs of the population in a particular region of goods and services.

It is possible to classify the market segment under different brands according to its mission. Consumer market classification focuses on the following criteria: type, structure of goods, organizational form, subject structure, geographical boundaries, economic and legal characteristics, demographic characteristics.

From the ensuing classification, there is a complete idea that the consumer market is a perfect, integrated system of complexes. The purpose of the research is to study the specific features of the formation and development of the regional consumer goods market, which is the main component of this system.

Specific features of the regional consumer goods market:

- Influence of internal, external economic, social and political situations (i.e. interregional commodity flows, labor migration, capital movements);
- Relative equivalence, which is reflected in the rules and traditions of trade turnover;
- variety of goods, which can satisfy different needs of the population of the region;
- availability of a large number of non-relative consumer goods sellers;
- availability of uninterrupted (daily) demand for consumer goods;
- availability of strategically important products affecting socio-economic situation in the region;
- formation of organizations that provide the main subjects of the consumer goods market with retail commodities, transportation and storage of goods;
- The relative high level of competition among manufacturers of foodstuffs in the region is relatively high [8].

As can be seen from the characteristics of the regional consumer goods market, this type of market, as a complex economic category, has a significant impact on the socio-economic situation in the regions and plays an important role in the production process.

The functioning of the regional consumer goods market differs between the needs of the population and the balance between supply and demand, the balance between the demand and supply of goods and services, the difference between the differentiation in income and consumption, the level of consumption and consumption, the current gap between consumption and savings, such

as the difference between individual forms.

Methods for the study of the regional consumer commodity markets include the size of the total demand for certain commodity groups and the supply volumes of these commodities; determining the ratio of retail trade turnover, the volume of sales of consumer goods, as well as the national and imported goods in the national market; analyzing the quality of goods entering the consumer market, building a description of regional retail chains, and studying the system of paid services [2].

The level of solvency, solvency, which determines the demand for products and services in the analysis and evaluation of the regional consumer goods market; Dynamics of mass production of goods in the region, weight, assortment of products imported from other regions and foreign countries; nature and quality of services rendered to the population, prices of products and their dynamics; sale of products; service is crucial.

We offer the following stages of the method of analysis of the economy of the region, reflecting its full and effective position in the field of production and sales:

At the first stage, a comprehensive analysis of the regional consumer goods market will be implemented [7]. This, in turn, allows the dynamics and composition of commodities to obtain information on their sources of access to the regional consumer market. It also emphasizes that the information received will provide information on the purchasing power of the region's population.

At the second stage, it is planned to assess the sensitivity of supply of the consumer goods market to external sources and to identify directions aimed at the development of effective inter-regional cooperation [1].

Given the results of the analysis of the third stage, the volume of the regional consumer market will be determined. In our opinion, we can divide the complex analysis of the regional commodity markets into three main categories:

1. The composition of the offer of goods. At the same time, it is envisaged to analyze the stock and retail trade turnover (total structure of retail trade turnover, commodity composition of retail trade turnover, household expenditures for procurement of goods).

2. Sources of goods supply. At the same time, the structure of imports (export) of goods supply and the study of production and supply of foodstuffs and non-foodstuffs by manufacturers in industrial, agricultural, auxiliary, personal farms are defined.

3. Monetary income of the population and their purchasing power. The proportion of per capita income and expenditures is determined by the fact that the purchasing power of income is dependent on the supply of goods. Based on the data obtained in the fourth (final) stage, trends of development of the regional consumer goods market will be determined in perspective [3].

The main provisions of the regional consumer commodity market development are the existence of a strong competition among consumers of goods and their consumers; The flexibility of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in any short-term opportunity is crucial to the development of the consumer market; the necessity of partial intervention of the state into the consumer goods market; the deepening of market relations requires producers to apply sophisticated mechanisms to attract new customers and maintain their existing markets on consumer goods market; control over the quality of products produced; increasing the share of domestic producers in the market; creating conditions for the export of products.

In the consumer goods market goods are divided into two groups: foodstuffs and non-foodstuffs. Consumers of these products are the only two groups, but its producers are different [6]. From this point of view, it is necessary to study the aspects of consumer goods market research separately.

SWOT-analysis of each region determines priority trends in the consumer market in the long run promotes sustainable growth of the market under the economic crisis [4]. The strengths and weaknesses in the analysis will help to define the inner environment of the region, to identify the aspects of the region, the features of the opportunities and obstacles, and to identify the strengths and capabilities of achieving economic risk.

SWOT analysis is based on the data collected in the conjunctural survey of consumer goods market and regional statistical office data. The result shows that the strengths and capabilities of the region have more potential than its weaknesses and obstacles. Such a realistic analysis of the situation helps to determine the opportunities available to solve the existing problems in the region.

Development of consumer goods market in the region:

First, it ensures high level of employment of the population and leads to an increase in their income.

SWOT-analysis of factors of development of the consumer goods market affects

	<i>Strength's (S)</i>	<i>Weakness (W)</i>
OFFER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - availability of qualified workforce; - rich natural resources; - high potential of thermal reserves, allowing to plant favorable climatic conditions and hothouse crops; - the region has a high share of the region in the production of cotton fiber, grain, meat and dairy products; - the potential of extractive and processing industries; - Rich cultural and historical heritage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low activity and low efficiency of innovative technologies and methods of production of consumer goods; - Inefficient use of agricultural potential for livestock breeding, fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture; - Lack of modern technologies in agricultural production, transportation, storage and processing.
Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presence of industrial enterprises with stable place in the market; - a convenient and beneficial geostrategic role The "Great Silk Road"; - development of transit networks (air, railway and highways); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Differentiation of regional zones at the higher level in IT development; - Low competitiveness of products produced in the region.
Demand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High level of job creation in the sphere of small business and entrepreneurship. - positive dynamics of growth dynamics of incomes and services of the population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rural enterprises do not fully meet the needs of the population in consumer goods; - Low social development in mountain, foothill, and soils.
	<i>Opportunities (O)</i>	<i>Treats (T)</i>
OFFER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - non-agricultural sector in rural areas expansion of production; - comprehensive and systematic involvement of highly innovative technology investments for the production of competitive products on the basis of effective processing of general and winter raw materials; - Construction of new plants for the production of manganese and potassium salts; - Sustainable development of livestock; - exploitation of home-based advantages; - availability and availability of small businesses for the processing of local raw materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of competitiveness in a number of products; - high levels of depreciation in fixed assets; - orientation of the industrial production structure to raw material production; - High level of depletion in the water infrastructure. - - relatively low level of activity of small businesses; - insufficient level of development of private entrepreneurship in the real sector of the economy; - Lack of home-based ideas.
Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement of market infrastructure; - saturation of the market with consumer goods produced locally; - Achieving a positive market conjuncture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The possibility of market intervention in the conditions of open economy; - The presence of the market entities in the most competitive conditions.
Demand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The development of domestic production will increase the incomes of the population; - Increase of consumer goods composition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the conditions of inflation, the population cannot save money to buy large commodities.

Secondly, enterprises are able to maximize their sales and profit. As a result of the first and second cases, the region's income base will be expanded. The revenue base of the region stimulates the growth of budget expenditures and demand for commodities and services for the development of market infrastructure. Third, this leads to an increase in demand for direct investment. [5] For the complex development of the regional consumer goods market, the author believes that the dynamic growth of the economy, the welfare of the population, the economic security of the country and the competitiveness of goods should be further developed. To achieve this, it is necessary to solve a number of major social, macroeconomic, investment, institutional, financial and other issues:

1. Creation of conditions for increasing the competitiveness of goods, i.e. elimination of disparities in the average prices, reduction of energy production, reduction of subsidies to state, regional authorities and economic entities.

2. Prepare conditions that will help expand the scope of domestic demand. For example, by reducing the poverty level and the income distribution of the population through the strengthening of targeted social protection, increasing the productivity of the production, increasing the employment of the population.

3. Expansion of internal sources of financing of investments through the growth of revenues, expansion of the funds accumulated by the real sector, savings accumulated by the population and the creation of favorable conditions for direct foreign investments into the consumer market.

4. Improving the competitiveness of market products, services and capital by increasing the role of small businesses and private entrepreneurship.

Conclusion

1. The stages of development of the consumer goods market in the Republic of Uzbekistan as the stages of the development of the consumer goods market in the republic: maintenance of the existing consumer goods production capacities, the introduction of the national currency, the implementation of the grain independence program (1991-1994); Superior development of the sectors producing consumer goods, the foundations of economic independence (1995-2000); focusing on the creation and development of export-oriented industries based on the development of import-substituting consumer goods (2001-2007); the program of measures on elimination and elimination of the global financial and economic crisis in Uzbekistan has been developed and put into effect (since 2008).

2. It is necessary to further strengthen the economic, organizational and investment base, contributing to the modernization of sectors and industries, which contribute to the sustainable development of the consumer goods market in the region.

3. Promoting the development of small business and private entrepreneurship through expanding the lending activity of microcredit institutions, insurance companies and commercial banks, promoting the creation of new jobs that increase the incomes of the population, deeply recycling consumer markets on local raw materials, providing competitive products. Developing fairs that exhibit seasonal, thematic, illustrative and new models of goods in regions for the sale of goods produced by entrepreneurs will be beneficial for both parties, consumers and producers.

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